

DEVELOPMENT OF SMART IRRIGATION SYSTEM MODEL BASED ON IOT FOR SUGARCANE SEEDLING

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Abstract

Main purpose behind the development of model is to give clarity of huddles work done by smart irrigation system. In IoT based system, main agenda was to identify status of the soil and environmental parameters such as soil temperature, soil moisture, humidity, water level, solar radiation etc. Based on data collected by sensor, it analyses frequently and provides irrigation to crops as per requirement. As whole system was micro controlled based, can be operated from remote location through wireless transmission. Results of height and number of leaves grown on crop shows us, how effect of stress and scarcity of water removed by smart irrigation system. Average height of seven crops within 25 days after sowing found to be 13.84 cm, which shows better than water stressed crop. Along with number of leaves were 1.43 were also better as compared to water scarce crop. It can be concluded that, it is easy and simple method to adopt in irrigation scheduling with high precision.

Key words: IoT, wireless transmission, micro controller, module, relay etc.

Introduction

In India 60-70% of the economy is based on post-harvest treatments, fertilizers, pesticides and herbicides etc. such as agriculture. But investment is more important than income. Investments are mainly in labor, water and fertilizer, and there is a great need for the adoption of modern agricultural practices in order to be productive. The underground water table is decreasing day by day due to the unplanned use of water. In addition, less rainfall and less groundwater will reduce the amount of water in the world.

Today, water scarcity is one of the biggest problems in the world. The Smart Irrigation System increases efficiency and is a new technology that improves water flow and saves water. Water supply technologies based on real soil and weather condition; thus enables farmers to save water in irrigation systems by using new technologies are suitable for their needs (Abedin et al. 2017). Irrigation holds the most promise for increasing food productivity and security, provided it is managed efficiently. To better manage the competing demands for water, agricultural policies will have to make water efficiency a priority. Hence the scientific and technology based irrigation scheduling of water is one of the ways to improve the irrigation processes to optimize the use of water and energy consumption. The incorporation of sensors in the context of agricultural production for water management and conservation has concerned an increasing interest for establishing irrigation management strategies.

Technologies such as the Internet of Things (IoT), smartphone devices, and sensors help farmers monitor soil temperature, water

Water Tank:

needs, weather etc. to understand the reality of their fields (Ayaz et al. 2019).

There are various benefits associated with IoT systems in irrigation and some of them could be considered as overall reduction in water consumption, high cost-efficiency, high performance efficiency, lesser energy consumption, lesser wastage of crops etc. (Garcia et al. 2020). Now a day, the internet is reached almost every corner of the world. By considering this we can take leverage to use Internet of things in agriculture.

Study area

Present work was conducted at the laboratory of department of irrigation and drainage engineering, Dadasaheb Mokashi College of Agricultural Engineering and Technology, Rajmachi, Karad.

Materials and Methods

A Soil Moisture Sensor is one kind of low-cost electronic sensor that is used to detect the moisture of the soil. This sensor can measure the volumetric content of water inside the soil. This sensor is consists of mainly two parts, one is Sensing Probs and another one is the Sensor Module. The probes allow the current to pass through the soil and then it gets the resistance value according to moisture value in soil.

Water pump

It is used to deliver or pressurizes a liquid. It transfers the mechanical energy of the prime mover or other external energy to the liquid, to transfer water from water tank to crop through mains, sub-mains and lateral.

Water tanks are used for storage of water, which was applied to sugarcane seedling at time of requirement. Water tank used for storage shown in above plate, having capacity of 100 L.

Plate 2: Water Tank**Irrigation system**

For irrigating the crop drip irrigation system was used. It consists of lateral pipes that emit water directly to the root zones of crops, and sub-main pipes that supply water to the laterals. Whole irrigation system builds on wooden board having dimension of 4 ft × 2 ft. mains and lateral ware laid along the length of wooden board, while

submain is perpendicular to the length of board. Layout of irrigation system was shown in plate 3.

Components:

Plate 3: Layout of Irrigation system

To check IoT based smart irrigation work properly, growth analysis of sugarcane seedling was done. Growth analysis parameters consist of height of crop and Number of leaves of crop, which is taken at 4-5 days of interval. Nomenclature for sugarcane crop decided on the basis of position of crops alignment with submain. Those crop grown right side of submain were R1, R2, R3 and R4, while, left side crops

were named as L1, L2 and L3, respectively.

Schematic diagram of IoT based smart irrigation system is shown in fig. 6. Irrigation system was design in such way that row to row spacing and plant to plant spacing were 15 cm × 20 cm. Position of other components of irrigation system such as soil moisture sensor, controller water pump and water tank etc. were dictated in fig. 6.

Specification

Volts	12 VOLTS
AMPS	4.5 A
Flow	4.5 (Lpm)
Press	140 PSI
Speed	3800 RPM

Plate 1: Water Pump

A product of turbo Diaphragm, Rainolux (IN)

Fig. 6: Schematic diagram of IoT based irrigation system

Power supply

Power supply for the irrigation system was provided by simply electric connection.

Software Implementation

ARDUINO IDE

Arduino IDE is an open-source programming which is basically used to write & compile code using a module called Arduino. This is official programming software which makes compiling of code simple, a typical man can understand the learning procedure. The IDE environment mainly contains two basic parts: Editor and

Compiler. Where, initially it is used for writing the code and later for compiling and uploading the code into the given arduino module. Arduino Software implementation is shown in fig.7. At the beginning when system starts, it initializes arduino to kick start sensors. A sensor starts to collect data as soon as it initiates and transfers to controller. Moreover, it monitors all the data collected and decides on or off the motor for irrigation. Decision was taken on the basis of set minimum and maximum threshold value of soil moisture status in soil.

Fig. 7: Flow chart of software implementation

Block diagram and circuit diagram of IoT based irrigation system shown in fig 8 and 9, respectively. As soon as power supply to NodeMCU it initiates the working. Further it simultaneously transfers the power to relay and signal to Android App (Blynk) for initiation

(On/Off) of water pump and display current scenario of irrigation system, respectively. During this period NodeMCU analyse data collected from soil moisture sensor and temperature sensor for further instruction regarding on/off of motor.

Fig.8: Block Diagram of IoT based smart irrigation

Fig.9: Circuit diagram of Iot based Smart Irrigation

BLYNK App

It was designed for IoT. It helps to control irrigation system remotely and provide soil moisture status information. It helps to visualize and store data. This platform has 3 main elements:

- 1) Blynk app – It helps to make interference with the project.
- 2) Blynk Server – Establishes a communication network between smartphone and hardware.

3) Blynk Libraries – All incoming and outgoing commands are processed and enables communication between server.

Result and Discussion:

Data for growth analysis for sugarcane seedling were taken after germination of crop with 4-5 days of interval. There results were shown in table below. Growth analysis parameters consist of height of crop and number of leaves of crop.

Plate 4: Layout of Irrigation System

First reading of growth analysis was taken on 31st August and after that 5th, 9th, 14th and 18th November, within 4 or 5 days interval, consequently. First reading, on 31st August average height of crop from seven seedlings found to be 7.14 cm with maximum 9 cm for R2 and minimum 6 cm of L2 and L3, respectively, at same time there were no leaves were observed. But opposite situation observed on 18th November (last reading), average height and number of leaves

were 19.86 cm and 3.14, respectively. During this period, irrigation scheduling was done on the basis of moisture content present in the soil. Soil moisture sensor measures the soil moisture in water fraction by volume (WFV or m³/m³). If soil moisture content (SMC) below 300 WFV or between 300 to 1000 WFV, water pump “on” automatically. While, SMC more than 1000 WFV, water pump “off” automatically.

Table 2: Analysis of cultivated sugarcane crop

Sr. No.		1	2	3	4	5
Date		31.10.22	05.11.22	09.11.22	14.11.22	18.11.22
R1	H, cm	8	11	15	18	20
	NL	0	1	1	2	3
R2	H, cm	9	13	17	19	22
	NL	0	1	2	2	3
R3	H, cm	6	10	13	16	19
	NL	0	1	2	3	4
R4	H, cm	8	12	16	18	20
	NL	0	0	1	2	3
L1	H, cm	7	9	14	17	20
	NL	0	1	1	2	3
L2	H, cm	6	8	10	13	19
	NL	0	0	1	2	3

L3	H, cm	6	8	11	15	19
	NL	0	0	1	2	3
Average	H, cm	7.14	10.14	13.71	16.57	19.86
	NL	0	0.58	1.29	2.14	3.14
Note : H – Height of Plant, cm			Average of Average		Height of plant	
NL – No. of Leaves					No. of leaves	
					13.84 cm	
					1.43	

Conclusion:

On the basis of above result it seems that design and implementation of a smart irrigation system was successful. This automated irrigation system was easily controlled by mobile. It act like an intelligent switching system, which on and off automatically on the basis of soil moisture content. Further it saves time and energy, which may be utilized for other necessary work.

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